
THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF ABDURAUUF FITRAT

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Annotation: This article reflects on the genesis of jadid literature and the jadid Abdurauf Fitrat who contributed to it. Jadid literature is aimed at awakening the nation. Abdurauf Fitrat is the Uzbek historian, philologist, translator, writer, playwright and poet, one of the founders of modern Uzbek language and literature, a well-known representative of Central Asian modernism, and the first Uzbek professor.

Key words: literature, jadid, movement, nation, poetry, Turkestan, people, progressives.

The abundance of scandals that characterized the XXth century not only made it stand out in the lives of Uzbek people but also in the lives of people worldwide. The pace of life processes has significantly accelerated by this century. The pace at which social events are exchanged has reached unthinkable proportions. At the start of this century, Turkestan's tranquil way of life—which had existed for several centuries—was completely upended. Turkestans now have different lives as a result of the advent of new ideas, technological advancements, and faster information sharing. Up to that point, our national literature and national life were not mutually exclusive. In the history of literature, each literary period has its own goals and objectives, new genres, and modifications of ideas. As a result, all of this is combined under one name. In particular, the period after the Russian invasion can be summarized as the literature of the national renaissance. Bibliographer Begali Kasimov divided this period into two periods: 1) Uzbek literature in the second half of the XIX century: sources and origins; 2) Uzbek literature in the first quarter of the XX century: development and completion⁴³.

The representatives of the Jadid movement often called themselves progressives, later Jadids. The advanced progressive forces of that time, first of all, the intellectuals, felt that the local population was lagging behind the global development and realized the need to reform the society. Jadidism was essentially a political movement. It has periods of formation and defeat, which can be conditionally divided into four. In Turkestan, Bukhara and Khiva, these periods are 1895–1905; 1906–1916; 1917–1920, 1921–1929⁴⁴.

⁴³ Avloniy.(2006) Tanlangan asarlar// II tom, Ma'naviyat. T.: -b 304

⁴⁴ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jadidchilik>

Literary scholars, linguists, historians, philosophers, and pedagogues have studied the scientific heritage of Abdurauf Fitrat to a certain extent. In particular, the life and work of the literary scholar H. Boltaboev, the enlightener, the state of his studies abroad, studied educational ideas as much as possible. B. Kasimov, one of the scientists who have sufficiently studied the Jadid movement, studied the life and work of Fitrat and analyzed some of his works⁴⁵.

Jadid literature was completely aimed at awakening the nation. The heroes of this literature were not the representatives of the upper class or figures irradiated with divine power, as in the previous period, but ordinary people who came from the masses, returned to them, and therefore had a greater opportunity to influence the people. Jadid writers tried to express new themes in new genres and through new images.

Abdurauf Fitrat (1886-1938) was an influential figure in the field of literature and culture in Central Asia, particularly in Uzbekistan. He was a poet, writer, playwright, and a prominent figure in the Jadid movement, which advocated for educational and cultural reforms in the early XXth century. Fitrat is the overall picture of the artistic world not through some taken works, but the whole creation through the research of dramaturgy not only allows to identify new aspects of literary creativity, but also can bring new conclusions and rules for the creation of literary theory and the artistic world of a certain creator. The main direction of the monograph is the principle of re-examination of the specific problems of the study of literary works and existing ideas in literary studies⁴⁶.

Fitrat went to study in Turkey in 1909 and studied at Istanbul Dorilfunu until 1913. He was active in the "Bukhara Education Maarif" association established in Turkey. Behbudi served to improve the modern schools founded by him. His first collection was published in 1911 under the name "Sayha" ("Chorlov"). Such works as "Traveler Hindi", "Munozara" were also published in these years. Fitrat was executed on October 4, 1938, among the great intellectuals of our nation, such as Abdulla Qadiri, Cholpon, Otajon Hashim, Qayyum Rhamazon, Ghazi Olim. Only by 1956 was he acquitted. He was acquitted, and only after another thirty-five years, thanks to the period of independence, was there an opportunity to tell and write the truth about him. Abdurauf Fitrat's life and literary work are characterized by a wealth of contradictions. On September 25, 1991, Abdurauf Fitrat was awarded the Republican State Prize named after Alisher Navoi for his services in the development of Uzbek dramaturgy, realistic literary criticism, and founding of the school of literary studies⁴⁷.

⁴⁵ Falsafa qomusiy lug'ati (tuzuvchi va ma'sul muharrir Q.Nazarov) –T.: Sharq, 2004- y, 496 b.

⁴⁶ Ganiyev I.Fitrat dramalari poetikasi.-Toshkent: Fan,2005. -B.9

⁴⁷ <https://tafakkur.net/abdurauf-fitrat.haqida>

Abdurauf Fitrat was a unique, highly skilled playwright. In the 20s, he created about a dozen dramatic works, and all of them were staged at that time. The fact that they played a big role in cultural life can be seen from the fact that each work was the cause of great discussions, and every time serious comments were made about our history, literary heritage, and daily affairs in connection with these works. Most of Fitrat's works are devoted to historical events, they describe the heroic traditions of the Tajik and Uzbek peoples, their struggle against foreign invaders, their tyranny, their thirst for justice and truth.

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